

Data and Methodology : Exploring How Digital Luthiers Choose Their Tools

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Digital luthiers (designers of digital musical instruments) work with a range of both software and hardware tools in order to realise the instruments they build. A digital musical instrument is a highly performant piece of technology with which a performer may interact. This leads to these devices being multifaceted artefacts that combine fields of design, user interaction, audio synthesis and more. In this paper, we present the methodology and data for a study that explores how these digital luthiers choose their tools for creating digital musical instruments.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: digital musical instruments, human computer interaction, programming languages

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper is published as a supplement to a study that explores how digital luthiers[8] (designers of digital musical instruments) choose their tools, both software and hardware. It was intended to be pre-published ahead of the data collection phase, however, due to time challenges related to the COVID-19 pandemic it is published following the initial interviews and ahead of undertaking analysis. In this publication, we present the data that was collected and the methodology that will be used to analyse this data. The data is formatted and presented to provide an element of confirmability to the resulting study and further, to encourage research and analysis that builds upon this work.

This study was designed to collect perspectives from a range of prominent instrument designers from a diverse set of backgrounds.

This study was ethically reviewed by the University of West England's Computer Science and Creative Technology Faculty Research Ethics Committee. Following approval, participants were invited to share their thoughts on digital musical instrument (DMI) design in the form of a standardised, open-ended, online interview. Each participant was issued with a comprehensive information pack describing the study and was able to withdraw from the study at any time while it was active. Participants provided written consent and were able to review their transcripts following the interview and before publication.

2 MOTIVATION

As our role as researchers inherently impacts qualitative data analysis we present our motivations. This study seeks to explore ideas based on three research questions:

Why and how do Instrument designers pick their tools?

What distinct problem spaces do instrument designers consider to be involved in instrument design?

How do instrument designers define a digital musical instrument?

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These questions stem from the larger context of our work, aiming to explore and develop more expressive tools for the creation of digital musical instruments, particularly programming languages. The study was initially designed to address the motivations for a PhD thesis, exploring topics that apply to the human-computer interaction (HCI) around developers of specialised technology, how they choose the technologies they use and what challenges they face. This work currently contextualises challenges faced by these developers in the notion of problem spaces as described by Goel and Pirolli [5] and further with regards to domains [7]. An inductive research approach was chosen to help broaden perspectives beyond the immediate research interests of the researchers, to identify the most salient issues identified by digital luthiers.

The final question addresses the notion of what constitutes a digital musical instrument - a surprisingly contentious topic that is exemplified by the debate as to whether the 'I' in 'NIME' (New Interfaces for Musical Expression) should be Interface or Instrument [10]. While this question less directly contributes to the immediate research aims, the study presents an opportunity to explore contemporary concepts, terms and attitudes that are present across the field. Whilst the value in providing a specific definition for a DMI remains debatable, it provides a thought-provoking question to explore in the context of an individuals perspective.

We view a qualitative research approach as the most effective method for understanding the very subjective aspects of HCI research that relates to the selection and use of tools and programming languages relevant to the domain.

3 PARTICIPANTS

Participants were directly invited based on their contributions to a range of novel digital musical instruments or association with an organisation that produces instruments. A subset of these instruments is listed in Section 3.2 and a selection of them is illustrated in Figure 1. The selection process follows a purposeful sampling strategy, selecting participants involved in designing novel digital instruments to capture a range of perspectives that are representative of the DMI design community and the various motivations they incorporate.

A loose set of categories were defined as a basis to draw participants from, these were; Commercial, Research, Community and Artist. Commercial and Research categories describe instruments whose motivations are for either commercial 'mass-market' production or coupled to a research process respectively. Community instruments largely encompass open source projects and small teams (or individuals) independently making instruments in low volumes. The Artist category represents instrument designers who build instruments to support their artistic endeavours. Of course, there is significant overlap with these definitions, however, drawing evenly from these groups helped to provide a balanced view of the community and the intentions for instrument design they represent.

Purposeful sampling was also selected to better distribute perspectives across genders, resulting in a more representative set of perspectives of the actual digital luthiers themselves, an approach that is supported by an ever-growing body of literature [9, 12]. This invite based selection process assisted in managing a more gender-balanced selection across participants and a variety of experience levels, however, we acknowledge a lack of cultural diversity in this study which is another important facet of this issue that should be accounted for in future work [11]. This could be likely be improved with a broader call in conjunction with the selection process used here, such that selection is not limited to the networking capacity of the researchers.

Participants were approached online and invited to participate or recommend a suitable participant. The sample size was intended to be between 24 and 32 participants, drawn equally from our previously defined categories. During this study, 27 participants were interviewed. A demographic of the population is provided in Table 1 and a selection of the participant's roles can be seen below (Section 3.1).

Gender		Ehtnicity		Age	
Male	14	white	21	18 - 24	1
Female	8	Asian	1	25 - 34	12
Non Binary	1	Lantinx	1	35 - 44	6
Prefer not to say	4	Brazillian	1	45 - 54	2
		Prefer not to say	3	55 - 64	4
				Prefer not to say	2

Table 1. Demographic of participant population.

3.1 Participant Roles

- Music Technology researcher and professor.
- Digital artist/performer/composer
- Artist
- Software Engineer
- Software Engineering Manager
- CEO
- Composer
- Founder
- Researcher and Lecturer
- Assistant Professor of Music Technology
- Composer & Instrument Builder
- Audio developer
- Researcher, designer, performer
- Software Developer
- Professor
- Electronic musician
- Software Engineer
- DSP Engineer
- Professor of Media Computing
- Hardware and software engineer
- Lead designer
- Composer and interactive hardware developer
- Creative director

3.2 Instrument List

- Soft Revolvers
- Alpha Sphere
- Knurl
- Artiphon Orba
- Reactable
- The Blade Axe
- Mutable Instruments Shruthi
- Claravox
- Polaron
- The Ladies Glove
- Linnstrument
- Cv
- Abelton Push
- Roli Seaboard Grand
- OTTO
- Winterbloom Sol DrumBud
- Electronic_Khipu_
- The daïs
- EMG instruments
- Gechologic Loopsynth
- Bastl Kastle Drum

Further, information gathered on the participants includes their familiarity with HCI literature and/or the NIME community and lists of their significantly used programming languages, hardware and software tools. For further details on the data set used (including the published data-set), see Section 6.

We also capture a rudimentary metric of experience in the form of years spent in the field and the number of instruments they have designed. We emphasise that this is a metric of limited insight that can poorly characterise a persons experience, however, in the selection process, attention was given to incorporating a range of experience levels when sampling participants.

Fig. 1. A selection of instruments from the study.

4 INTERVIEWS

Interviews were conducted as standardised open-ended interviews, with 22 participants engaging with an interviewer via video call and five via email, following an internal pilot study with peers that had DMI design experience. Interviews had a duration of 20 - 60 minutes at the discretion of the participant. Interviews took place between 25th January 2021 and 1st April 2021. Participants were provided with a copy of the questions to use as a reference during the interview. All interviews were carried out by the lead author.

Standardised open-ended interviews were selected to allow extensive exploration of a small set of topics, with a direction lead by the interviewee. The interviewing style focused on allowing the participant to explore the questions with minimal interaction from the interviewer and questions were largely left open to interpretation by the participant.

If required, clarifications were made and included in transcripts. This approach was taken to allow for the data collected to be reviewed in other styles whilst still working for our reflexive analysis approach, described in Section 5

Interviews were recorded (audio only) and transcribed verbatim, then processed to ensure appropriate confidentiality and IP protection. In the case of email interviews, emails were formatted to match transcripts.

5 ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In this study analysis is based on a phenomenological perspective, exploring the personal perspective of digital luthiers. Because of its fit with an inductive approach and its capacity to create a rich and nuanced view of these interviews, reflexive thematic analysis based on Braun and Clarke's framework [2] was selected as the methodology for analysis. This study focuses on using a reflexive approach for analysis [1], exploring the perspectives of the many digital luthiers that have introduced their ideas to this study in an approach Alvesson, Hardy and Harley describe as multi-perspective practices. Notably, a varied set of perspectives and motivations have been captured in this data set and this study looks to draw out ideas from these different perspectives. With quite broad questions presented in the interviews, this analysis explores the topic largely inductively intending to explore the explicit semantic concepts introduced by participants, though consideration will also be given to latent, underlying meaning where relevant.

In line with Braun and Clarke's [3] description of reflexive thematic analysis, we recognise that as researchers we play a role in the generation of qualitative information [6]. To support this we also provide a descriptive background of the researchers taking part in this study at the end of this publication, aiming to make clear some of our biases. The wealth of introspective resources and writing from Braun and Clarke help us as computer scientists better leverage qualitative analysis [2].

5.1 Methodology

This methodology somewhat contrasts the peer validated approach typical of research based on grounded theory [3]. In this study, two coders will analyse all transcripts. Coders will regularly meet to discuss codes throughout the coding process and iteratively generate themes from the coded transcripts using the Quirkos software tool. Coders will also periodically present and discuss these themes and narratives with the rest of the research team. This approach aims to ensure we are generating codes and themes that draw on the knowledge and experience of the research team [4].

In line with Clarke and Braun's process for reflexive thematic analysis, the approach for analysis follows the following steps:

- Data familiarization period for reviewers
- Data coding using Quirkos software
- Generation of themes
- Discussion between researchers on themes, reflection and development
- Iteration around steps 2-4
- Refining and naming themes and developing of ideas around themes
- Writing paper; discussion of themes

6 DATA

Interview transcripts and corresponding data are available from the following repository:

<https://github.com/muses-dmi/dmi-design-study>

This repository contains the transcripts as individual documents, a comma-separated value (.csv) file of quantified data and any resources (scripts or guides) that are developed in the course of this study and may be of wider use. Transcripts are formatted as Markdown, with a metadata section at the start formatted as YAML. An example can be seen below that demonstrates the data related to each transcript. Participant numbers are randomly assigned numbers suitable for referencing transcripts.

Note: This is a metadata section formatted in YAML.

```
participant: 1
role: Music Technology researcher and professor.
experience(years): 30
instrument_count: 10
```

```
instruments:
- FMOL
- Reactable
- Many more
```

```
languages:
- c++
- puredata
```

...

In the body of the transcript, questions are denoted with a single '#' at the start of the line. These were read aloud to the participant (but also provided in written form for reference).

Any communication from the interviewer is denoted with a single '>' character at the start of the line. (When rendered as markdown this will render the interviewers comments as a blockquote).

7 NOTES ON CONTRIBUTORS

Nathan Renney is a PhD student at the University of West England, Bristol, UK. His thesis explores how the development of modern programming languages can be used to influence digital lutherie, the process of designing digital musical instruments. With a background as a musician, his research interests include using programming languages to be more expressive, both musically and beyond. As part of the Physical Computing Research Group at UWE, Nathan primarily works with embedded and real-time systems with an interest in the application of functional programming and type systems.

Dr Benedict R. Gaster is an Associate Professor at the University of West of England, he is the co-director of the Computer Science Research Centre, within which he also leads the Physical Computing group. His research focuses

on the design of embedded platforms for musical expression and more generally IoT. He is the co-founder of Bristol LoRaWAN a low power wide area network for Bristol city and is the technical lead for a city-wide project on pollution monitoring for communities, having developed UWE Sense (a hardware platform for cheap sensing). Along with his PhD students and in collaboration with UWE's music tech department, he is developing a new audio platform based on ARM micro-controllers using the Rust programming language to build faster and more robust sound! Previously Benedict worked at Qualcomm and AMD where he was a co-designer on the programming language OpenCL, including being the lead developer on AMD's OpenCL compiler. He has a PhD in computer science for his work on type systems for extensible records and variants.

Dr Thomas Mitchell is an Associate Professor in Creative Technologies, at UWE Bristol where he leads the Creative Technologies Laboratory. He is also an honorary scholar at the University of Bristol, resident at the Pervasive Media Studio and a Member of the Computer Science Research Centre and Bristol Robotics Laboratory. He is a co-founder of MiMU Gloves Limited, a technology start-up that he co-founded to enable musicians to perform with gestures. Connecting physicality and sound, Tom's work exploits new affordances of motion capture and extended reality technologies to inspire questions about music, art and science.

Harri Renney is a PhD student studying computer science at the University of the West of England. Specialising in the optimisation of digital audio processes for heterogeneous systems, he focuses on designing software tools for mapping processes to Graphics Processing Units, a now nearly ubiquitous hardware acceleration device that uses massively parallel processing architectures. Harri believes that with the advancing state of technology, powerful physical modelling audio processes will become increasingly viable, opening up a whole new range of possibilities in the field of digital audio.

8 CITATIONS

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